

Background

The cultivation of perennial cereals might represent an economically and ecologically interesting option for extensive cultivation, particularly in marginal land.

Locations

The 3 locations differ in the type of soil and in the amount of precipitation. Due to poor soil quality at all locations, annual wheat can only be grown to a limited extent.

Breeding Lines

5 breeding lines of perennial wheat (*Triticum aestivum* × *Thinopyrum intermedium*) and a mixture of the 5 breeding lines were sown at three sites in Bavaria

2 varieties of annual wheat for comparison: 'Capo', 'Livius'

Breeding lines were selected from a bulk originating from Washington State University

Other plots were additionally sown with white clover and subterranean clover

Results

In the 1st year, the grain yields of the perennial breeding lines were 49 to 96% of cv. 'Capo', which reached an average of 17.4 dt/ha

In the 2nd year, the yields were 9 to 38% of 'Capo', which reached an average of 10.8 dt/ha

The re-emergence in autumn was significantly affected by severe drought at all locations in the 1st and 2nd year and showed differences between the lines up to a total failure at one location.

In the 3rd year, the yields of the perennial breeding lines were very low. The yields of the plots with under-sown clover were significantly higher in the third year.

A significant increase of soil organic carbon was observed in the order perennial with clover > perennial > annual in the subsoil of one location. Two of the three locations showed a significant increase of microbial biomass in the same order both in top soil and subsoil. The number of earthworms was up to twice as high in perennial relative to annual wheat.

Conclusion

A third year of cultivation cannot be recommended under these climatic and soil conditions.

A mixture with a low growing clover species is recommended because of better weed suppression.

Perennial cereals are an interesting option for the production in organic agriculture especially on marginal land in order to reduce erosion and improve soil fertility.